

Identification of Novel Cancer Biomarkers Using Machine Learning on RNA-seq Data

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Abstract

Cancer is the second worldwide cause of death after cardiovascular diseases, hence, early and precise diagnose is essential. An accurate diagnosis is key for the optimal treatment of cancer patients. Most recent and advanced ways in prediction is molecular diagnostics which offers precise, fair, and efficient breast cancer classification, but are not widely applied in clinical settings. Aim of this study is to integrate and combine RNA-seq data along with machine learning approaches to identify novel cancer biomarkers of potential clinical and biotechnological value.

Keywords: cancer biomarkers, gene expression analysis, Machine learning, RNA-seq

Introduction

Cancer is referred to unusual cell division in human tissue due to genetic changes. Gene expression is significant in early detection of cancer as it presents the biochemical processes of cells, tissue and an organism. Deoxyribonucleic acid (DNA) microarrays and ribonucleic acid (RNA)-sequencing methods can produce crucial data for computational analysis by evaluating the expression levels of genes. In recent decade, Machine Learning (ML) algorithms have been used in many various field related to healthcare systems, especially for disease prediction and classification tasks. Integration of molecular omics data with ML algorithms has offered a great hope and opportunity to classify and analyze clinical data. RNA sequence (RNA-seq) analysis are being considered as the gold standard for transcriptomics analysis. (Figure 1)

Figure1. Data collection and analysis in case of cancer prediction

Materials and Methods

1.1 Data Collection and RNA-seq Dataset Description

DNA fragment to a recognized genomic or transcriptome source is based on the gene expression quantification that is the comparison of the sequenced reads related to the number of base pairs sequenced. The precision of the quantification hinge on the sequenced reads having sufficient distinctive data to allow the application of bioinformatics algorithms to correlate the reads to the suitable genes. One of the frequent methods for estimating gene expression include DNA microarrays and next-generation sequencing (NGS) methods. The DNA microarray method indicates a two-dimensional array with microscopic spots to which short sequences or genes bind to known DNA molecules through a hybridization process. NGS methods of massively parallel sequencing offer extraordinarily adaptability and speed for high-throughput analysis. Also they have been used in the nucleotide sequence of a full genome or of a single DNA or RNA segment determination. RNA-sequencing or RNA-seq is an NGS method used in conversion of RNA molecule into cDNA (complementary DNA) which indicates the nucleotides sequences in order to analyze and quantify the gene expression. DNA microarrays provides higher specificity and resolution, enhanced sensitivity to various expression and larger dynamic range compared to RNA-seq (Table1). However, they can be applied for any species examination of RNA determination at a specific time. RNA-Seq is used for gene expression measurement and variations examination. The different applications are based on the capacity to analyze all RNA molecules in a cell or tissue, including protein-coding RNA (mRNA) and non-coding regulatory RNA such as miRNA and siRNA or functional RNA like tRNA and rRNA which are suitably measure their abundances simultaneously. Other important qualities of RNA-Seq include its high resolution and large dynamic range, which have resulted in a large volume of acquired data and contributed to significant progress in transcriptomics research.[1]

Characteristics	Microarray Data	RNA-Seq Data
Gene Discovery	No	Yes
Different Isoform	No	Yes
High Resolution	No	Yes
Background Noise	Yes	No
High Cost	Yes	No
Rare/New Transcript	No	Yes
Noncoding RNA	No	Yes

Table1. Comparison of Microarray data and RNA-seq data.

2. Preprocessing and Normalization of RNA-seq Data

RNA-Seq data of 17,471 transcripts from a total of 3,244 cancer samples across 26 different tissue types were compiled and collected from in-house sequencing data and publically available in International Cancer Genome Consortium and The Cancer Genome Atlas datasets. Cancer biomarker signatures were extracted using a 10-fold cross-validation method of log transformation, quantile normalization, transcript ranking by area under the receiver operating characteristic curve, and step wise logistic regression.[2] To conduct the required data to analyze, for example, single-cell RNA sequencing analysis, it remains imperative to filter the data prior to analysis. The number of total unique molecular identifiers (nUMIs), the number of expressed genes (nGene) and the percentage of transcripts from mitochondrial (per.mito) or ribosomal genes (per.ribo) were widely used to perform cell quality control (QC). Since solid tumor cells demonstrate a heightened tendency for stress in the course of sample dissociation, list of genes associated with sample dissociation was created and use the percentage of this gene list as another QC index (per.diss). To account for potentially varied distributions in quality control metrics across different sample sources and experimental conditions, adaptive determination the filtering thresholds, which involved the detection of the outlier data-points from the distribution of the quality control metrics, instead of relying on fixed cutoffs in a constant behavior(Figure 2).[3]

Figure 2. An overview on application of RNA-seq to ML usage.

3. Differential Gene Expression Analysis

In biomarker discovery and the application of machine learning from the RNA-Seq data is mainly focused on genes, however, recent studies have demonstrated that transcript-based analyses exceed gene-based analyses by using ML [4]. In order to classify and analyze obtained data, it is crucial to examine pre and post result which in this case is gene expression. In the attained predicted list from results, multiple biomarkers can be identified that contribute to the distinction of different cell types from the different regions of cancers. Genes in such a list have been confirmed to distinguish at least two groups of cells according to recent publications. In some research, top genes are chosen for detailed analyses. Finding a specific gene leads to indicating that the gene may help distinguish tumor cells from normal cells. In May 2020, another study revealed that TYROBP (name of a gene used in diagnosis of lung cancer) was found to be one of the most significant biomarkers reflecting the immune status of tumor microenvironments and contributing to the distinction of functional and dysfunctional immune cells. Therefore, the gene may play a massive role in distinguishing between normal and tumorous lymph node tissues because of differences in immune characteristics under physical or pathological (tumorigenic) conditions. [5]

Table 2. Examples of gene expression profiling. [6]

Title/Description	Normalization Methods	No. of Samples	Percentage of Cancer
Novel biomarker discovery for stratification and prognosis of breast cancer patients	MAS5 signal intensity	62 (58 breast tumor + 4 normal breast)	94%
Breast cancer gene expression analysis	Log2 GCRMA signal intensity	121 (104 breast tumor + 17 normal breast)	86%
Expression data from human breast tissue	RMA expression value	50 (43 breast tumor + 7 normal breast)	86%
Human breast tumor expression	GCRMA calculated signal intensity, log2 transformed	47 (40 breast tumor + 7 normal breast)	85%
Identifying breast cancer biomarkers	RMA expression values	66 (54 breast tumor + 12 normal breast)	82%
Stromal molecular signatures of breast and prostate cancer	Log2 RMA signal	12 (6 breast tumor + 6 normal breast)	50%
Identifying novel anti-angiogenic targets in human breast cancer	Log2 RMA signal	6 (3 breast tumor + 3 normal breast)	50%
Differential effect of surgical manipulation on gene expression in normal breast tissue and breast tumour tissue	Log2-normalized signal	18 (6 breast tumor + 12 normal breast)	33%

4. Machine Learning Model Development and Training

Machine learning (ML) is a multidisciplinary field that take place in use of computer science, artificial intelligence, computational statistics, and information theory to make algorithms that learn from existing data and make predictions on new data. Duo to the speed in data analyzing, attention has been drawn to omics technologies in life sciences and clinical analysis and ML is being applied to increasingly more areas. Prediction of diseases is one of the most important applications of ML. High accuracy in disease prediction can be reached by analyzing the gained data from individuals. These techniques provide essential information about the pathogenesis of diseases at metabolite, protein, and transcriptome level. Transcriptomics is the general analysis of organism's transcriptome or the sum of all RNA transcripts. Transcriptomics have been used to understand nature of diseases and to find diagnostic and prognostic biomarkers. High throughput RNA-seq data could provide an opportunity to analyze hundreds of transcripts for a complete view of the expression dynamics of diseases. ML, which is a branch of artificial intelligence, provides computers the ability to create models from data. It has been used in many fields of healthcare. In particular, using health records in ML systems provides vast opportunities to answer clinical problems. Another promising area in healthcare is omics technology. Recent developments in genomics, transcriptomics, proteomics, and metabolomics have opened new opportunities for personalized and precision in medicine and treatment. Omics have been used to understand disease mechanism, treatment efficacy, and lifestyle interventions for diseases. In the last decade, the number of data produced in omics technologies has been enhanced exponentially. The idea of integrating omics data with ML methods is to provide more comprehensive understanding of biological systems. More specific, evaluation of clinical omics studies has opened a new feature in diagnosis and prognosis of diseases. In this study, different evaluation methods were used to test the performance of ML and DL models over the data. The first metric of this study was classification accuracy, which was calculated by the ratio of the number of correct predictions to the total number of samples/predictions. The accuracy will be high if most of the samples are correctly predicted.

$$Accuracy = \frac{\text{Number of correct predictions}}{\text{Total number of predictions}} \quad (1)$$

The second metric that was used in this study is the Root Mean Square Error (RMSE), which is a widely used method to measure the gap between classification predictions and actual classes. The equation to calculate RMSE can be seen in (2):

$$RMSE = \sqrt{\frac{\sum_{n=1}^N (r_n - \hat{r}_n)^2}{N}} \quad (2):$$

In Equation (2), \hat{r}_n is predicted values, r_n is observed values, and N is the number of observations. The results of RMSE are lower when the correct classification is employed.[7]

5. Biomarker Identification for Cancer Diagnosis and Prognosis

Development in precise medication and treatment has raised the popularity of genes application in case of disease diagnose and prognosis. Biomarkers or biological markers are being used to identify or track certain biological events and process. Biomarkers are molecules such as genes, DNA, proteins, and metabolite that signify whether a process going on in the body is normal or abnormal, and it can be used as a symptom of any disease or disorder. Biomarkers are generated from the cancer tissue, and they can be present in any part of the body, including stool, blood, tumor tissue, urine, body fluids, and any other tissue or cell. Biomarkers are found in every disease, including cancer, multiple sclerosis, diabetes, and heart diseases. Seven types of biomarkers exist which are risk, diagnostic, prognostic, predictive, monitoring, safety, and response biomarkers (figure 3). The biomarker identification process can be divided into three sections: identification of diagnostic, prognostic, and predictive biomarkers using omics data with the ML and DL approaches. In one research, machine learning algorithm RF (Random Forest) was applied to identify novel diagnostic biomarkers which are the markers applied for confirmation the present of disease specially in different sub-type of cancer, in this case, in hepatocellular carcinoma. miRNA genes of 373 patients were downloaded from TCGA data and passed to the Random Forest model for biomarker identification. The experiment was validated on the GSE63046 dataset. The results found that the proposed method identified five diagnostic biomarkers. Other researches using machine learning algorithms comprising RF and SVM, and it was investigated that 11 top-ranked miRNAs as biomarkers can be beneficial in predicting breast cancer and are treated as diagnostic biomarkers. In another, machine learning algorithms was introduced to identify the transcripts for prediction and guide the treatment related to prostate cancer progression. [8]

Figure3. Common cancer biomarkers

Results and discussion

In this review, it can be estimated that using RNA-Seq data combined with machine learning approaches can aid in finding novel transcript biomarkers. In various recent study, identification of biomarkers in different type of cancers such as breast and lung cancer, hepatocellular carcinoma, using RNA-seq and ML has shown a great promise in early detection of cancer. Artificial intelligence and machine learning approaches for the identification of novel diagnostic and prognostic gene signature biomarkers. Further study can enhance and develop the speed of data collection and classification. Development in this field can lead to precise medication and personalized treatment.

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